

ASSESSMENT OF PATIENT SATISFACTION WITH PRE-OPERATIVE ANESTHESIA ASSESSMENT IN CESAREAN SECTION SURGERIES

Rasab Umar Sohail^{*1}, Tayyaba Ayub², Khadija Akhtar³, Ahmad Faraz⁴, Amina Waheed⁵, Awais Khan⁶

^{*1,3,4,5,6}Department of Emerging Allied Health Technologies, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, The Superior University, Lahore

²Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, The Superior University, Lahore

^{*1}bsat-f21-011@superior.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Rasab Umar Sohail

bsat-f21-011@superior.edu.pk

Abstract

Objective of Study : To determine the impact of preoperative anesthesia assessment on patient's satisfaction in C section surgeries . To study the impact of Anesthesia team communication, Patient's counseling, Anxiety or stress management by anesthesia team , Pain Management , Information given about NPO , possible complications like PONV and Consent on the Patient satisfaction in c-section surgeries.

Research Design: The research design for the proposed study will be a descriptive cross sectional study and data will be collected on prestructured questionnaire from patients undergoing c section surgeries and meeting the selection criteria.

Place & Duration of Study: The research will be conducted at Anesthesia Department of Chaudhry Muhammad Akram Teaching and Research Hospital Lahore From January 2025 to March 2025..

Material & Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Anesthesia Department of Chaudhry Muhammad Akram Teaching and Research Hospital Lahore From January 2025 to March 2025. A sample of 120 patients undergoing elective cesarean section was selected out of which 0.9% refused and remaining 107 were considered for the study. Parturients who cannot communicate and who were unconscious after the operation were excluded. These all of the patients who meet our criterion were asked to fill the questionnaire that helped to determine the impact of different parts of pre operative anaesthesia assessment on patient satisfaction. The Frequency, percentage, and correlation of patient data were evaluated by the SPSS statistics V.30.

Results: One hundred and eight consecutive patients who underwent for elective cesarean section over 2 months were originally enrolled in the study. Out of these 0.9% refused to take part in the study . 80% of the population were satisfied with fasting instructions, 59.8% of patients were satisfied with clarity of information on possible post operative complications and anesthesia risks, 22.4 % were neutral in this case. 78.5% were satisfied with professionalism of anesthesia team. 69.2 %

were satisfied and 17.8% were neutral on information provided about anesthesia consent form. 71.1% were satisfied with management of any discomfort. 67.3% were satisfied with anesthesia team help in alleviating anxiety about anesthesia. 67.3% were satisfied for participation in decision making regarding the procedure. Overall satisfaction with preoperative anesthesia assessment was 24.3% were extremely satisfied 54.2% were satisfied 11.2 percent were less or not satisfied and 10.3% were neutral.

Conclusion: We concluded that the process of preoperative anesthesia assessment ensures safety for anesthesia which contributes to increase the surgical outcomes and increase in patient's satisfaction. Patient satisfaction is an important outcome indicator of the quality of health care services, as recognized by the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA). Preoperative anesthesia assessment is a major step of anesthesia services in any institute and plays a key role in patient satisfaction. In our study Majority of participants were satisfied with preoperative interaction with the anesthetist, delivery of fasting instructions, clarity about the procedure however improvement is needed in delivery of clear information about possible complications of procedure and consent about anesthesia.

INTRODUCTION

The preoperative evaluation of a surgical patient is an essential activity for the anesthetist as it represents its first direct interaction with the patient. The ultimate goals of preoperative medical assessment are to limit the patient's surgical and anaesthetic perioperative morbidity or mortality while returning him to desirable functioning as soon as possible. This evaluation serves two purposes: to allow the anesthetist take a proper note of their patient's health conditions (preoperative assessment), and provide information on risk factors related with anesthesia; as well educate patients, review types/methods of anesthesia, discuss postoperative management options etc.(1).

The goals of the preoperative evaluation were to gain information regarding the patient's current status, co morbid conditions and grading of patients for surgical procedures(2). This informs decisions regarding laboratory or investigative work-up that may be needed prior to the procedure. The preoperative meeting and examination provides the anesthesiologist an opportunity to meet the patient and their parents or guardians.(3)

This provides an area to develop rapport, outline anesthetic risk, and present the anesthetic plan for the day of surgery include NPO times, premedication, and options for postoperative analgesia. There should also be ample time for

questions to be answered and for informed consent to be obtained.

Specified assessment techniques such as the Prior to Anaesthesia Assessment Form (PAAF), assist guarantee full assessments and informed consent, which improves patient outcomes(4).

For full pre-anesthesia examination, the Research Centre, Pakistan Kidney and Liver Institute (RC&PKLI) uses the Prior to Anaesthesia Assessment Form (PAAF), which is based on international standards. (5). This is combined under obtaining consent. The patients are informed about the planned anesthesia and possible complications which might occur during perioperative evaluation. Preoperative anesthesia evaluations are crucial for adapting anaesthetic plans to individual patients, enhancing safety, decreasing complications, and relieving anxiety.(6)

Patient satisfaction after a preoperative anesthesia assessment is generally high when the patient feels adequately informed about the procedure, has their concerns addressed, experiences a reduction in anxiety due to the consultation, and feels confident in the anesthetist's ability to manage their care during surgery; key factors include clear communication, addressing anxieties, and providing sufficient information about the anesthetic plan. The results of a study suggest that information does

influence the experience of pain after surgery and related psychological factors. The postoperative pain declined more rapidly for patients in the treatment group, the degree of preoperative state anxiety was lower and they were more satisfied with the postoperative pain management(7).

The non-technical aspects of medical care, particularly the interpersonal dynamics that arise during specific instances of care, can be evaluated through patient satisfaction.(8)

Patient satisfaction is a significant indicator in healthcare, reflecting their thoughts and emotional reactions to their care experiences. It considers expectations, service quality, and prior experiences. The level of patient approval is an important indicator of high-quality healthcare. Patient satisfaction is important in anesthesia care, according to a 2013 ASA poll. Despite some skepticism, surveys are becoming increasingly important. (9)

Various factors can influence maternal satisfaction. Mothers encounter differing perceptions regarding the care they receive; the urgency of surgical procedures and demanding schedules often result in insufficient communication. Additionally, complications and side effects associated with spinal anesthesia are frequently identified as potential risk factors.

The American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) has indicated that future reimbursement for anesthesia services may be partially contingent upon patient satisfaction metrics. It is essential to evaluate the level of satisfaction and the factors that contribute to it in order to ensure the quality of care in anesthesia. Patient satisfaction is an important outcome indicator of the quality of health care services, as recognized by the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA).(10)

The degree of satisfaction and its influencing factors can vary significantly across different environments due to differences in caregivers, maternal sociodemographic characteristics, and the specific context of care. Consequently, this study seeks to evaluate the satisfaction levels and associated factors among parturient who underwent cesarean sections with spinal anesthesia. (11)

This patient satisfaction level with preoperative anesthesia assessment can also be different in hospital in the same city. This is because of the

difference in the approach of the anesthetists of different hospitals during their interactions with patients and difference in protocols set up for preoperative anesthesia assessment in these hospitals, which mainly includes providing information about post-operative pain and possible modes of analgesia, Post-operative nausea vomiting and its management, state of mind after anesthesia and different maternal aspects. Preoperative assessment plays a crucial role in the process of obtaining informed consent. While anesthesia services vary globally, they should strive to be as thorough as possible.(12)

METHODOLOGY

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Anesthesia Department of Chaudhry Muhammad Akram Teaching and Research Hospital Lahore From January 2025 to March 2025. A sample of 120 patients undergoing elective cesarean section was selected out of which 0.9% refused and remaining 107 were considered for the study. Parturients who cannot communicate and who were unconscious after the operation were excluded. These all of the patients who meet our criterion were asked to fill the Questionnaire, that includes questions regarding information (age, surgery, type of anesthesia, prior c-section and satisfaction questions). The purpose of the questionnaire was to gauge the level of contentment felt by the patients with preoperative interaction with anesthetist and the effectiveness of preoperative assessment on maternal satisfaction.

Chi square test paired sample statistics were applied in order to examine the relationship between variables like age, previous c section, anesthesia team communication, pain management, anxiety management by anesthesia team, information about procedure and consent. The level of significance was set at 0.05 at 95% confidence.

Descriptive statistics include frequencies, percentages and means. Charts and tables were added in this paper using this study statistical software. The Frequency, percentage, and correlation of patient data were evaluated by the SPSS statistics V.30.

RESULT

One hundred and eight consecutive patients who underwent for elective cesarean section over 2

months initially participated in the research. Among them, 0.9% declined to participate in the research. Fasting instructions were well-received by 80% of the population, and 59.8% of patients felt that information on potential problems after surgery was clear and understandable and anesthesia risks, 22.4% were neutral in this case. 78.5% were satisfied with professionalism of anesthesia team. 69.2% were satisfied and 17.8% were neutral on information

provided about anesthesia consent form. 71.1% were satisfied with management of any discomfort. 67.3% were satisfied with anesthesia team help in alleviating anxiety about anesthesia. 67.3% were satisfied for participation in decision making regarding the procedure. overall satisfaction with preoperative anesthesia assessment was 24.3% were extremely satisfied 54.2% were satisfied 11.2 percent were less or not satisfied and 10.3% were neutral.

Type of Anesthesia:					
		Frequency:	Percent:	Valid Percentage:	Cumulative Percentage:
legitimate	General Anesthesia	25	23.4	23.4	23.4
	Regional Anesthesia	82	76.6	76.6	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 1: The table shows the type of anesthesia used during the C Section of these 107 patients. 82 out of 107 patients underwent regional anesthesia and the remaining 25 patients underwent general anesthesia.

Figure 1: shows the type of anesthesia used during the C Section.

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 to 25 Years	33	30.8	30.8	30.8
	26 to 30 Years	52	48.6	48.6	79.4
	30 to 40 Years	21	19.6	19.6	99.1
	41 Years	1	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Identifies the age range of patients having a cesarian section. Ages ranged from 18 to 25 for 33 patients, 26 to 30 for 52, 30 to 40 for 21 individuals, and 41 for only 1 patient out of 107.

Figure 2: A Pie chart showing the age groups of the participants.

Previous C Section Experience						
		Number of occurrences	%	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Validity Rate	No	43		40.2	40.2	40.2
	Yes	64		59.8	59.8	100.0
	Total	107		100.0	100.0	

Table 3: This table shows the previous history of C Section of the participants. Out of 107 64 patients had a C Section procedure in past and 43 did not had previous C Section surgery.

Figure 3: A pie chart showing the history of C Section among the patients. 60 percent of the participants had a history of C Section in the past and 40 percent did not.

Residence					
		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Validity Rate	Rural	41	38.3	38.3	38.3
	Urban	66	61.7	61.7	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: The participants' residences are included in the table. 41 out of 107 patients belonged to rural areas and 66 to the urban.

Figure 4: Shows the residence of the patients participating in this study.

Education					
		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Validity Rate	Educated	62	57.9	57.9	57.9
	Uneducated	45	42.1	42.1	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: This table shows the literacy among the patients. 62 out of 107 patients were educated and remaining were uneducated.

Figure 5: A bar chart showing the education of the patients participating in the research.

Past anesthesia experience					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	37	34.6	34.6	34.6
	Yes	70	65.4	65.4	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 6: The table presents the past anesthesia experience of the participants. 37 out of 107 patients had no anesthesia history and 70 patients had a previous anesthesia history.

Figure 6: A bar chart showing presenting the past anesthesia experience of the patients.

Complications from past Anesthesia					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Apnea	1	.9	.9	.9
	Back pain	12	11.2	11.2	12.1
	Back pain, Headache	3	2.8	2.8	15.0
	Back pain, Headache, Hypotension	2	1.9	1.9	16.8
	Back pain, Headache, Nausea vomiting,	1	.9	.9	17.8

Hypotension				
Back pain, Nausea vomiting	1	.9	.9	18.7
Headache	5	4.7	4.7	23.4
Headache, Hypotension	1	.9	.9	24.3
Headache, Nausea vomiting	1	.9	.9	25.2
Hypotension	10	9.3	9.3	34.6
Nausea vomiting	9	8.4	8.4	43.0
Nausea vomiting, Hypotension	2	1.9	1.9	44.9
No	3	2.8	2.8	47.7
No Complications	48	44.9	44.9	92.5
Nothing	8	7.5	7.5	100.0
Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 7: This table show the complications occurred during the previous procedure among the patients. 1 out of 107 had a history of post-operative apnea, 12 patients had back pain, 3 had back pain and headache, 2 had back pain, headache and hypotension, 1 had back pain, headache, nausea vomiting

and hypo-tension, 1 had back pain and nausea vomiting, 5 had headache, 1 had headache and hypotension, 1 had headache and nausea vomiting, 10 had hypotension, 9 had nausea vomiting, 2 had nausea vomiting and hypotension and 59 had no complications.

Figure 7: Presenting the complication among the patients during previous procedure.

Rate your satisfaction with explanation of the Anesthesia					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	35	32.7	32.7	32.7
	Less Satisfied	12	11.2	11.2	43.9
	Neutral	15	14.0	14.0	57.9
	Not Satisfied	2	1.9	1.9	59.8
	Satisfied	43	40.2	40.2	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 8: The anesthetist explained the anesthesia and its types to the patient. This table shows how much the patients were satisfied with the information provided by the anesthetist. 35 out of

107 patients were extremely satisfied, 43 were satisfied, 15 were neutral, 12 were less satisfied and 2 were not satisfied with the information provided about the anesthesia.

Figure 8: A pie chart representing the satisfaction rate of patients with the anesthetist’s explanation of anesthesia and its types.

Satisfaction with preoperative fasting instructions					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	45	42.1	42.1	42.1
	Less Satisfied	12	11.2	11.2	53.3
	Neutral	10	9.3	9.3	62.6
	Satisfied	40	37.4	37.4	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 9: This table presents the satisfaction level of the patients with the preoperative instruction. 45 out of 107 patients were extremely satisfied, 40 were satisfied, 10 were neutral and 12 were less satisfied.

Figure 9: A pie chart presenting the satisfaction of patients with the preoperative instruction given by the anesthesiologist.

Satisfaction with the clarity of information provided about possible postoperative complications					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	17	15.9	15.9	15.9
	Less Satisfied	16	15.0	15.0	30.8
	Neutral	24	22.4	22.4	53.3
	Not Satisfied	3	2.8	2.8	56.1
	Satisfied	47	43.9	43.9	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 10: This table shows the clarity of information and instruction provided by the anesthesiologist. 17 out of 107 patients were extremely satisfied, 47 were satisfied, 24 were neutral, 16 were less satisfied and 3 were not satisfied.

Figure 10: This pie chart shows the satisfaction of the patients with the clarity of information provided by the anesthetist.

Satisfaction with professionalism of anesthesia team					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	32	29.9	29.9	29.9
	Less Satisfied	11	10.3	10.3	40.2
	Neutral	9	8.4	8.4	48.6
	Not Satisfied	3	2.8	2.8	51.4
	Satisfied	52	48.6	48.6	100.0
Total		107	100.0	100.0	

Table 11: This table presents the satisfaction of patients with the professionalism of the anesthesia team. 32 out of 107 patients were extremely satisfied, 52 were satisfied, 9 were neutral, 11 were less satisfied and 3 were not satisfied.

Figure 11: A pie chart presenting the professionalism of the anesthesia team.

Rate your satisfaction with the information consent form provided about about anesthesia consent form					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	29	27.1	27.1	27.1
	Less Satisfied	13	12.1	12.1	39.3
	Neutral	19	17.8	17.8	57.0
	Not Satisfied	1	.9	.9	57.9
	Satisfied	45	42.1	42.1	100.0
Total		107	100.0	100.0	

Table 12: This table shows the satisfaction of the patients with the information provided by the anesthetist about the consent form. 29 out of 107 were extremely satisfied, 45 were satisfied, 19 were neutral, 13 were less satisfied and 1 was not satisfied.

Rate your satisfaction with the information provided about anesthesia consent form

Figure 12: A pie chart presenting the satisfaction rate of the patients with the information provided about the consent form by the anesthesia team.

Proper care and attention to safety and well being					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	30	28.0	28.0	28.0
	Less Satisfied	11	10.3	10.3	38.3
	Neutral	16	15.0	15.0	53.3
	Not Satisfied	1	.9	.9	54.2
	Satisfied	49	45.8	45.8	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 13: This table shows the satisfaction of the patients with the care and attention paid to them by the anesthesia team. 30 out of 107 patients were extremely satisfied, 49 were satisfied, 16 were neutral, 11 were less satisfied and 1 was not satisfied.

Proper care and attention to safety and well being

Figure 13: A pie chart presenting the satisfaction of the patient with the care provided by the anesthesia team.

Satisfaction with the management of any discomfort					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	31	29.0	29.0	29.0
	Less Satisfied	15	14.0	14.0	43.0
	Neutral	14	13.1	13.1	56.1
	Not Satisfied	2	1.9	1.9	57.9
	Satisfied	45	42.1	42.1	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 14: This table presents the satisfaction of the patients with the management of discomfort or pain during the procedure. 31 patients were extremely satisfied, 45 were satisfied, 14 were neutral, 15 were less satisfied and 2 were less satisfied.

Figure 14: A pie chart presenting the satisfaction of the patients with the management of discomfort during the procedure.

Rate your satisfaction with help in alleviating anxiety about anesthesia					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	23	21.5	21.5	21.5
	Less Satisfied	17	15.9	15.9	37.4
	Neutral	16	15.0	15.0	52.3
	Not Satisfied	2	1.9	1.9	54.2
	Satisfied	49	45.8	45.8	100.0
Total		107	100.0	100.0	

Table 15: This table shows the satisfaction of the patients with the management of anxiety. 23 were extremely satisfied, 49 were satisfied, 16 were neutral, 17 were less satisfied and 2 were not satisfied.

Rate your satisfaction with help in alleviating anxiety about anaesthesia

Figure 15: A pie chart showing the satisfaction of the patients with the management of anxiety during the procedure.

Rate your participation in decision making about the type of anaesthesia					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	27	25.2	25.2	25.2
	Less Satisfied	14	13.1	13.1	38.3
	Neutral	20	18.7	18.7	57.0
	Not Satisfied	1	.9	.9	57.9
	Satisfied	45	42.1	42.1	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 16: A table presenting the satisfaction of the patients with participation in the decision making. 27 out of 107 patients were extremely satisfied, 45 were satisfied, 20 were neutral, 14 were less satisfied and 1 was not satisfied.

Rate your participation in decision making about the type of anesthesia

Figure 16: This pie chart shows the patients satisfaction with the participation in the decision making about the type of anaesthesia.

Overall satisfaction with Pre-operative anesthesia assessment					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Extremely Satisfied	26	24.3	24.3	24.3
	Less Satisfied	12	11.2	11.2	35.5
	Neutral	11	10.3	10.3	45.8
	Satisfied	58	54.2	54.2	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Table 17: This table shows the overall satisfaction of the patients with the preoperative anesthesia assessment. 26 out of 107 patients were extremely satisfied, 58 were satisfied, 11 were neutral and 12 were less satisfied.

Overall satisfaction with Pre-operative anesthesia assessment

Figure 17: A pie chart demonstrating the patients' general satisfaction with the preoperative anesthesia assessment.

DISCUSSION

Preoperative anesthesia assessment is an important process for all surgical procedures. This interaction between anesthetist and patient. The anesthetist is permitted to assess the patient's medical condition, anesthesia options, possible complications which may arise from the anesthesia or surgical process and options to cope up with possible complications.

This whole process of preoperative anesthesia assessment ensures safety for anesthesia which contributes to increase the surgical outcomes and increase in patient's satisfaction. The American Society of Anesthesiologists has acknowledged that that contented patients are better able to judge the quality of the treatment they received.(ASA) (13).

Preoperative anesthesia assessment is a major step of anesthesia services in any institute and plays a key role in patient contentment. In this article 80% of the population were extremely satisfied or satisfied with fasting instructions,59.8% of patients were satisfied with clarity of information on possible post operative complications and anesthesia risks,22.4 % were neutral in this case.78.5% were satisfied with professionalism of anesthesia team.69.2 % were satisfied and 17.8% were neutral on information provided about anesthesia consent form. 71.1% were

satisfied with management of any discomfort 67.3% were satisfied with the anesthesia team's help in alleviating anxiety about anesthesia 67.3% were satisfied for participation in decision making regarding the procedure. Overall satisfaction with preoperative anesthesia assessment was 24.3% were extremely satisfied 54.2% were satisfied which is cumulative 78.5%, 11.2 percent were less or not satisfied and 10.3% were neutral. These results of our study were more satisfactory The was carried out between March 1, 2020, and April 30, 2021, at the University of Gondar Comprehensive Specialized Hospital. This study aimed to assess the level of satisfaction that mothers had with the preoperative anesthetic assessment process for patients who had elective cesarian sections. It was shown that 68.2% of patients at the preoperative anesthetic assessment this study were instructed to fast. Furthermore, during the preoperative period, the following percentages of parturients were provided with information: (61.2%), (55.4%), (52.2%), and (33.8%). This information pertains to the anesthetic used, any side effects, ways to deal with discomfort after surgery, and whether or not you could have nausea or vomiting after the procedure. Anesthesia students have already seen 75.8% of the

patients.(14).

Nevertheless, the results of our study were less gratifying when contrasted with an audit conducted in Sri Lanka, which demonstrated that 95% of the 300 patients audited were examined by anesthesiologists prior to surgery.

Before Surgery fasting instructions were administered to 94.39% of patients; however, only 42.1% were informed of the type of anesthesia they would undergo prior to surgery. Additionally, 35.44% of individuals were informed about the mood of anesthesia. In 94.38% of the population, the aggregate satisfaction was greater than 50%. Only 83.86% of patients' inquiries were addressed, and 96.14% of patients reported feeling at ease during the preoperative visit.(15)

Conclusion

We concluded that the process of preoperative anesthesia assessment ensures safety for anesthesia which contributes to increase the surgical outcomes and increase in patient's satisfaction. Patient satisfaction is an important outcome indicator of the quality of health care services, as recognized by the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA). Preoperative anesthesia assessment is a major step of anesthesia services in any institute and plays a key role in patient satisfaction. In our study Majority of participants were satisfied with preoperative interaction with the anesthetist, delivery of fasting instructions, clarity about the procedure however improvement is needed in delivery of clear information about possible complications of procedure and consent about anesthesia.

There should be improvement in areas like information about postoperative complications, consent taking process for anesthesia and addressing patient's anxiety about anesthesia. Continuous implementation of preoperative guidelines being followed in the hospital should be ensured.

There are always some limitations present during research because this study lacks the response from patients undergoing surgeries other than cesarean section. Qualitative approach was used which might impact the results of overall patients' satisfaction which could be higher in quantitative approach.

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